

THE IMPORTANCE OF VITAMINS IN THE HUMAN BODY

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Abstract: A person can eat various things in his daily life. It contains various substances and vitamins. Vitamins A, B, B1, B2, B6, B12, C, D, PP, K are extremely necessary for the human body. Their influence plays a very important role in the functioning of the human body. If one of these vitamins is lacking, the conditions for the emergence of various diseases are created in the human body. This article provides information about the importance of vitamins in the human body.

Key words: vitamin, beriberi, multivitaminosis, hypovitaminosis, hypervitaminosis, medicinal herbs, biotin, asparagine, serine, carotene, catechin, flavonol.

Vitamins are important for humans and animals are organic compounds in chemical structure. Too little for the body required (different from protein, fat and carbohydrates) these compounds are enzymes enters the molecule and participates in the exchange of substances in tissues. For the first time, the important role of vitamins in the functioning of the body was recognized in 1880 by the Russian scientist, pediatrician N.I. Lunin studied. Since then, doctors, biologists and other specialists have paid great attention to the study of the action of vitamins on the body and their role in various processes. Correction of multivitamin deficiency should be aimed not only at additional consumption of the missing substances, but also at improving their absorption, as well as at the synthesis of vitamins in the body. The human and animal body receives most vitamins only from plants with food. Therefore, food products contain a vitamin absence or lack of substances in the human or animal body metabolic disorders, and later as avitaminosis and hypovitaminosis causes the occurrence of serious diseases. Vitamins play an important role in the life of plants. They are substances the main regulator of metabolism - participates in the biosynthesis of enzymes. Many vitamins combine with proteins to form enzymes. Some vitamins, amino acids (for example, vitamin H-biotin, asparagine, serine, etc participates in the metabolism of amino acids. Vitamin C, carotene, catechins and oxidation of flavonols that occurs continuously in plant tissues and actively participates in the return process. During this process, vitamins for a certain time inside it is oxidized and reduced. Productivity of plants under the influence of vitamins increases, ripens faster and roots develop faster. Some vitamins (carotenoids) and participates in the process of photosynthesis and pollination of plant flowers. Biosynthesis of vitamins - almost all vitamins are in the plant organism is synthesized. Compounds that form only vitamins A and

D are provitamins after being synthesized in plant tissues and transferred to the animal organism, they become a vitamin. The course of vitamin biosynthesis in plant tissues has not yet been fully determined in experiments.

A person can eat various things in his daily life. His diet contains various substances and vitamins. For the human body A, B, Vitamins B1, B2, B6, B12, C, D, PP, K are extremely necessary. Their influence on human health plays a very important role in the activity of the organism. If any of these vitamins is not enough, conditions are created for the origin of various diseases in the human body.

Vitamin A. If this vitamin is reduced in a person's body, his eyesight will decrease, including he will not be able to see in the dark. It has been found that fatigue also occurs as a result of a lack of this vitamin in the body. In addition, due to the lack of vitamin A, the human body becomes salty, the hair becomes dry, and the nails become soft. This vitamin is more abundant in carrots, tomatoes, green peas, melons, oranges, and dairy products.

If vitamin B1 and its group are reduced, a person may feel nervous, memory decreases, nerves become irritable and appetite suffocates. These are found in oats, barley bread, mutton and a number of others in products.

When vitamin B2 is reduced in the human body, tears stop flowing, anemia occurs, the person becomes desensitized, the lips become shriveled, lips wrinkles also appear on it. It is found in eggs, lamb, yeast and cheese. As a result of a decrease in vitamin B6 in the body, a person's heart plays will remain. It is found in barley bread, cabbage, carrots, zucchini, raisins, cheese and fish.

When vitamin C is reduced in the human body, pain in the gums occurs, joints start to hurt, wounds don't heal quickly, and people get tired quickly will remain. It is found in potatoes, cabbage, bell pepper, various mushrooms, strawberries, it is found in large quantities in lemons and oranges.

Due to the lack of vitamin D in the human body, the sun hits it quickly his hair starts to fall out. This vitamin is more abundant in dairy products will be.

Intestinal, liver and kidney diseases due to lack of vitamin K it beats more, the blood doesn't clot well. This vitamin is found in onion, cabbage, pumpkin, blueberry. It is found in peas, beans, greens, liver and eggs.

If there is a lack of vitamin E, the activity of the sebaceous glands in the body is disturbed. Such without it, the hair turns gray and falls out quickly. This is found in rye, buckwheat bread, with rice food, there is a lot of cornmeal and liver. The vitamins mentioned above are different if they are lacking in the human body negative changes may occur. Falling off of nails, on the neck. These include frequent rashes and sores on the face. In these diseases it is recommended to use more walnut, sunflower, hemp oil. Currently, about 13 vitamins are known, they are proteins, fats and to ensure the normal functioning of vitamins together with carbohydrates should be in the diet of people and animals. In addition to vitamin There is a group of similar substances, it has all the properties of vitamins, but are not strictly required components of food. It is not a vitamin, but it is a precursor for their formation in the body compounds that can serve as provitamins. These include, for example, carotenes, which break down in the body and form vitamin A, into vitamin D some circulating sterols (ergosterol, 7-dehydrocholesterol, etc.) are included.

Many authors consider one of the aspects of child psychoneurology – various micronutrients in the resistance to acute and chronic stress emphasize the role. Pediatric when prescribing vitamin and / or mineral preparations neurologists treat a wide range of diseases of the central nervous system (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, etc.), as well as prefer complex drugs for somatoneurological pathologies. In neonatal neurology, certain vitamins are used for preventive purposes. Or for therapeutic purposes. in almost all types of diseases, because vitamins and minerals ensure the functioning of the nervous, endocrine, immune and other systems are trace elements. The problem of vitamin and / or mineral deficiency in children remains relevant at present. Therefore, it is necessary for children vitamins and minerals should be subsidized according to the age needs of the body. Many studies have shown that food in early childhood daily content of vitamins, minerals and other biologically active substances deficiency contributes to the development of chronic diseases, in particular the activity of the immune system and the body's resistance to adverse environmental factors. decreases, metabolic processes are also disturbed. As a result, polysystemic over time pathology is formed, which quickly becomes chronic. As mentioned above, usually several vitamins and trace elements at the same time there is a lack of elements, which complicates the clinical picture and makes diagnosis difficult. Many chronic diseases, dysfunctions and It is assumed that susceptibility to infections is related to subclinical vitamin deficiency It is done because vitamins provide sufficient immunity, xenobiotic metabolism in the functioning of systems, as well as the body's antioxidant potential plays an important role in formation. while maintaining resistance to environmental factors is of great importance. Polyhypovitaminosis of one or more bioelements given that it is combined with deficiency, correcting it only through diet very difficult.

Caused by lack of certain vitamins in food they started calling beriberi. If the disease is a deficiency of several vitamins if it occurs due to, it is called multivitaminosis. Most of the time you need a vitamin you have to deal with relative scarcity; this is called hypovitaminosis disease. If the diagnosis is made in time, then beriberi and especially easily treat hypovitaminosis by introducing the appropriate vitamins into the body possible Excessive introduction of some vitamins into the body leads to hypervitaminosis may be the reason.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the correction of multivitamin deficiency is not only lacking additional consumption of substances, but also improving their absorption, and also include ensuring the synthesis of vitamins in the body need The main part of VMK is the recommendation of the most important vitamins and trace elements includes doses. But by completely absorbing all the components will not happen, because often in patients with a multivitamin deficiency, the intestine microbiota disturbance is also observed, which is in IUD reduces the availability of ingredients used. Thus, the main tactics in pediatrics are aimed at prevention, because own development of vitamin deficiency during vitamin therapy and their helps prevent the consequences. It should be remembered that consumption of VMK to do not only for children with impaired health, but also fruits and berries regardless of seasonal consumption, it is necessary for healthy children throughout the year. The best option is VMK with prebiotics, probiotics and bifidobacteria will be taken together, it will improve the state of intestinal microbiota, different prevention and treatment of diseases (obesity, diabetes, allergies, etc.) provides.

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